

Democratic Governance and Infrastructural Development in Enugu State, 1999-2019

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Abstract

The relationship between democracy and development is one of the major theoretical arguments put forward for justification of the drive towards the universalization of the neo-liberal ethos under the aegis of globalization. According to the purveyors of neo-liberalism, democracy is not just the only moral and legitimate way by which a society can be ruled, it also provides the needed nexus between governance and development. Thus, democracy not only prescribes how political power should be acquired but also what to do with it or how it should be exercised to ensure the good lives of the citizens. Regardless of the debate over the actual meaning of development, it is generally accepted that the state of infrastructure in any nation is reflective of the state of development of such a nation. In this regard, the return to multiparty democracy in 1999 held a ray of hope for the tackling of the myriad of Nigeria's developmental challenges, especially the infrastructural decay that characterized the long years of military rule. Sixteen years of democratic governance in Nigeria has left many observers wondering whether democracy is indeed the pathway to development given the appalling state to which infrastructure has degenerated in most Nigerian States. Even though several scholars have examined the relationship between democratic governance and infrastructural development in Nigeria, generally this study focuses specifically on democratic governance and infrastructural development in Enugu State between 1999 and 2019. The study adopted the theory of prebendalism as its theoretical framework of analysis, and also used descriptive research method as means of sourcing information through documentary method. This study argues that the poor infrastructural development in Enugu State is linked to the fact that government functionaries are not inclined to the people's yearning for democratic dividends. We therefore, found among others that democratic governance has not impacted fully on infrastructural development in Enugu State, and recommends that leaders should pay particular attention to the people's needs.

Keywords: Democracy, Democratic Governance, Development, Infrastructure, Human Welfare.

Introduction

The democratic governance framework is deeply rooted in the liberal democratic and neoliberal economic agenda (Adejumobi, 2004). According to Omodia & Aliu (2013), the state is expected to practice and promote constitutionalism, respect for the rule of law and human rights, popular participation, accountability and transparency, and probity in the management

of people and resources. Ikpi (1997), also argues that democratic governance can be examined from six perspectives such as; the initiation and maintenance of rapid socio-economic growth, the establishment and development of a free market economy, the establishment of basic organizational framework to act as a springboard for further development, the creation of an absorptive capacity for capital and other inputs, the promotion of private sector investment and the raising of the productivity of the people by improving their skills, enterprise, initiative, adaptability and attitudes. These values largely represent the core essence of democratic governance. Significantly, these key attributes are critical to capacity of democratic governance to engender and strengthen the social contract, popular trust, state legitimacy and enhance socio-economic and political development in the society (Omodia and Aliu, 2013).

As a result, majority of Nigerians are disenchanted with most of the outcomes of the current democratic experience of the fourth republic on their socio-political and economic wellbeing, as evident in the massive decline in popular trust in democratic institutions, processes and political leadership can be appropriately understood and situated (Aliu, 2014). Tragically, this development seems to have overshadowed some of the successes associated with the democratic experience of the current democratic governance in Nigeria. The uninterrupted character of the democratic transition and improvement in civil, political freedoms and liberties for example, appeared to have been lost to the popular lamentation over the failure of the democratic experience.

The Proponents of liberal democracy have vehemently argued that democratic governance, among other things, ushers in societal development, inclusion and participation of citizens in governance, accountability and transparency on the part of government officials, but the reverse is the case as Nigerians cannot actually be said to have meaningfully enjoyed the dividends of democracy since the advent of democratic governance in 1999.

Against this back drop, this study explored the interface between the sustenance of democratic governance and the improvement of infrastructure in Nigeria, using Enugu State as the focus of analysis. It equally examines governance process in Nigeria under the current democratic dispensation. This is with a view to determining how the quality of Nigeria's democracy has impacted on its ability to deliver the dividends of democracy to the citizenry so as to ensure the protection of economic and fundamental human rights, and as well ensure the improvement of the infrastructure and human developments in our societies.

Theoretical Perspective

This study is essentially predicated on the theory of "Prebendalism" theorized by Richard Joseph, on his work published in 1987. Richard Joseph's "theory of prebendal politics" provides and provokes stimulating analysis of Nigerian federalism. The theory shows that the constituent ethnicities of Nigeria's federal society are the bases for the organization, mobilization, and legitimization of prebendalism's ethno-clientelistic networks of patronage, corruption, and rent seeking. Similarly, the innovative Nigerian principle of "federal character," according to which the country's ethno-regional diversity must be reflected in all governmental appointments and disbursements, has effectively transformed into prebendalism or the personal, factional, and communal appropriation of public offices, from an informal norm of political competition into a directive principle of state policy, as claimed by Joseph (1987).

In a seminal 1987 study of Nigeria, the political scientist Richard Joseph argued that the country's political culture was strongly influenced by the fact that holding public office provided officials with access to resources and that the theft of such resources went largely unpunished. Joseph called this system "prebendalism," likening it to European feudal practices.

The contributors to this volume use the prism of prebendalism to look at the permanent struggle in Nigeria over access to public resources, which structures the way Nigerians perceive citizenship, shapes the country's complex and sometimes contentious ethno-dynamics, contributes to growing social inequality. The problem is that although the dismal performance of the country's economy has always been largely due to egregiously high levels of governmental malfeasance, and the true extent of public corruption in Nigeria today is difficult to determine.

Since the end of the Cold War and the subsequent shift in political and economic relationships between the global North and South, the demand for good governance has become the shorthand for changing the scope of exercise of authority in aids-seeking nations from 'government' towards 'governance' with transparency, accountability, inclusiveness and wider scope for human rights, all becoming recurrent vocabularies. What is also often encoded in good governance is the fight against corruption. In response, most Sub-Saharan African governments have experienced decades of anti-corruption programmes initiated with the support of multi-national agencies. While it is acknowledged that much progress has been made, the pace is however, discouragingly slow especially in countries like Nigeria and Kenya.

This study therefore, argues that understanding the differential foundational structures which breed corruption in various African states especially Nigeria, is central to achieving substantial progress in anti-corruption fights by designing the appropriate counter-mechanisms. In the light of current corruption scandals and political events in Nigeria, the study examines prebendal politics in Nigeria as theorized by Joseph (1987) to postulate the trajectory of Nigeria's political economy into the future.

Corruption is ubiquitous (Ogundiya, 2009) but because of centrality of public policy and management to national, social, economic and political outcomes, most academic discourses on corruption focus on political corruption and corruption in government sector while relegating corruption in the private sector to the background. This present study is not an exception and the definitions briefly discussed here are targeted at political corruption – the issue which the author seeks to examine in chronological detail with reference to Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarifications

Democracy and Development

Democracy has been viewed by different scholars based on their experiences. This accounts for different definitions of democracy. Democracy is a concept that does not have any universally accepted definition, but in spite of the differences in conceptualization and practices, all versions of democracy share one fundamental objective of “ how to govern the society in such a way that power actually belongs to all people”.

Chafe (1994) argued that democracy is the involvement of the people in running the political, socio-economic and cultural affairs of the society. The degree of involvement of people in the total control of their polity, within the standard of natural justices, determines the degree of democratic substance of a political system (Sadeeq, 2008). This shows that the peculiar virtue of democracy is thought to lie in the fact that it is only government that can advance the interests of all the members of a politically organized community (Barry, 1992). Schumpeter (1954) defined democracy as an institutional arrangement for arriving at political decisions in which individuals acquire the power to decide, by means of a competitive struggle for the people’s vote.

Moreover, Held (1982) conceptualized democracy as a cluster of rules and institutions permitting the broader participation of the majority of citizens in the selection of

representatives who govern them. In summation of varied definitions of democracy, it is deduced that democracy provides opportunities for the people to freely exercise their franchise in the selection of their representatives and leaders, this type of exercise excludes the use of force and coercion through the state apparatus.

What is clear that electoral democracy advances social and political rights? This concept tends to give greater premium to the professionalization of public policy with strong emphasis on political parties and civil society. This approach loses sight of the fact that citizens make democracy. However, there is a global trend towards the replacement of citizen democracy by consumer democracy, with citizens conceived as consumers, clients and users, government services increasingly seen as commodities and access based on the ability to pay. Across the continent civic identity is being replaced by consumer identity, cooperation by sectarian conflict, the creation of commonwealth by conflicts over the distribution of private wealth, citizen participation by apathy and disengagement and everyday politics by career politicians. In Africa, it has been observed on the declining public interest in elections, increasing citizen's disengagement from public affairs and distrust of government. Divisions characterized along left-right political leanings exemplify present day politics. The bitterness of this division limits the scope of citizens to work collaboratively in partnerships with government for common social goods. It fosters conflicts among citizens, communities and organized interests. Democracy is conceived in terms of a struggle over the distribution of wealth and private accumulation rather than the creation of commonwealth.

One of the U.S. political theorists by name Boyte, captured the adverse implications for citizens. According to Boyte (2004), When politics becomes the property of professional elites, bureaucrats and consultants, most people are marginalized in the serious work of public affairs. The question of democracy has largely neglected issues of economic justice basic needs such

as access to food, shelter, medical care and housing. In the absence of equal opportunity for all citizens to these essentials for human existence, the equality being opportunity for all citizens to these essentials for human existence, the equality being stressed in liberal democracy is defeated.

According to Gordon (1998), Democratic citizenship is undermined if there is too great contradiction between the egalitarian norms of a democratic polity and the inequalities of individuals and groups in civil society. Glaring inequalities undermine democracy in two basic ways; first, by fueling social discontent and political instability and second, through the persistence of poverty, by excluding more or less extensive sections of the population from access to the political process and its fruits.

It is at this stage that some African scholars have critiqued liberal democracy. For example, Awa (1991) averred that democracy must be made to deliver some economic empowerment and a higher state of living for the people. A democracy that cannot deliver on the basic needs of the people will be short-lived. Concerned this way, democracy and development must go hand in hand. In other words they are mutually reinforcing. Thus in the view of some scholars, socio-economic justice is at the heart of democracy (Otive and Omano, 2003). Similarly, the assumption that liberal democracy will promote good governance and hence reduce violent conflicts in Africa has been challenged (Adetula, 2011).

Most African countries have from 1990s transitioned from authoritarian rule to various forms of democratic government. The reintroduction of multiparty politics has not changed the nature of governance in many African countries and has therefore, had little or no effect in mitigating violent conflict. Electoral politics have indeed generated many contradictions for most young democracies, which are experiencing mixed political outcomes, often including violent political conflict. It produced undesirable results that threaten peace and security in Nigeria in particular and other African countries in general.

Consequently, development is apparently one of the most used concepts in the Third World countries of which Nigeria is among. The reason for this is because virtually everybody in this country, both the leaders and the followers are all interested in development. Therefore, what actually constitutes development?. Thus, while the leaders were busy dishing out figures to suggest that development is taking place, the people do not agree as their living conditions have not improved at all or in some cases getting worse.

Therefore, the result according to Obi (2005), was that after many years of implementing policies fashioned by Western Development Agencies and Scholars, the Third World Nations (Nigeria inclusive), found themselves neck deep in poverty and in some cases got poorer. It then followed that if all the development theories, programmes and policies which have been forced on our countries as key to development have not worked after so many decades, it then meant that either the conceptualization of development is faulty or the approaches towards realizing it is faulty or perhaps both.

However, when we talk of development in this study, we mean sustainable human development which is anchored on democracy coupled with a government that is responsible for providing the socio-economic needs of the people so as to bring progressive change in the lives of the peoples. This is the type of development that takes care of the well-being of the peoples, the environment and future generation into consideration in all efforts at development and appealing to the conscience of government and private institutions to do what is right (Sampson, 2013).

Link Between Democracy and Development

Scholars like Przeworski (1990) and Lamungi (2007) used cross national study to compare regimes (both democracies and dictatorships), and their effects on development; while

Pel (1990) study used human right development index (HRDI), per capita income, and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as indicators for measuring development among countries. Of course the studies have exposed some issues relevant to development in countries, however, there is little evidence of study with focus on poverty, unemployment, revenue and government expenditure, GDP growth and human development index, foreign exchange rate (Naira per US dollars) and health performance.

Considerable numbers of scholars including, (Pel, 1999; Campos 1994; Jamo 2010) maintain the view that, there is link between democracy and development, while others including Sirowy and Linkels (1991); Bardhan (2002); Przeworski and Lamongi (2007) on the contrary maintain the opposite view. Two approaches according to Somolakae (2007) were observed, the first approach utilized by the scholars was the normative approach by exploring the possible link on the basis of what they know about democracy and development, and try to establish possible linkages between them. While the other approach is the use of case studies by trying to operationalize the concept of democracy and development, and examining the rate and character of development within the area under study and try to establish conclusion whether relationship or linear association exist between the two variables. Duncan et al (2009 as cited in Olarimoye, (2010) maintain that there is clear relationship between political and economic change. However, there is limited hard evidence on the direction of casualty, and the basic mechanisms through which politics affect growth and vice versa. Chan (2009) in his study on democracy and development in Japan and some Asian newly industrialized countries, examined whether developing countries need to adopt democracy or western model to achieve economic success. The study argues that, economic and social freedoms are necessary, but not western style institution or culture.

The study is of the view that, liberal democracy is not a prerequisite for development, what is important for development is social and economic rights rather than the western ideology. Development can be achieved irrespective of the type of regime, so far social and economic freedoms are available. This view is also consistent with that of Sirowy and Linkels (1991); Bardhan (2002); Przeworski and Lamongi (2007) that there is negative relationship between democracy and development. They further opined that, regimes do not differ in their impact on the growth per capita income.

On the contrary, Barrow as cited in Pel, (1999) suggests that, the relationship between democracy and growth is likely to be slowest in the most politically repressed societies. But improvement in political rights and civil liberties in such societies tends to produce higher growth research in addition, and shows that growth tends to peak when the level of democracy is in the middle-range and gradually taper off as the level of democracy rises. The study also supported the notion that, positive linkages exist between democracy and development depending on the level of political and civil rights available, therefore the study maintained that, the higher the level of political and civil rights the higher the development, vice versa.

In similar study, (Pel, 1999) argued that, the question whether democracy promotes development rests on the central idea that political institutions critical to economic development are more likely to exist and function effectively under democratic rule. The institution include the rule of law which protects property rights, individual liberty which fosters creativity and entrepreneurship, the freedom of expression which ensures the production and unimpeded flow of information, and institutional checks and balances that prevent massive theft of public wealth often observed in democracies. Supporting this assertion, statistical study of growth data for 115 countries from 1960-1980 were utilized. Although, the work did not provide criteria for selecting the sampled population, however, it provided a comparative

analysis for several countries using institutional approach to analyze the level of development without due concern on the level of development of such institutions and that of such countries. Similar empirical study was also repeated and claims that, countries with high degree of political openness achieve an average annual per capital growth rate of 2.53 percent, compared with 1.41 percent in more closed political system. The study implies that more democratic countries may grow 80% faster than less democratic countries. Similar study also conducted examining GNP growth data from 100 countries from 1960-1990 but shows negative relationship. Again, Duncan et al (2009) also posited that, there is limited hard evidence on the direction of casualty, and the basic mechanisms through which polities affect growth and vice versa.

Scholars opposing this view contended that strong authoritarian state which they view as essential or leading a successful process of development. They argued that, only strong authoritarian state that discipline groups bent on making too many demands and hence undermining the development agenda. Others asserted that democracy opens political contexts that may take the form of ethnic and religious mobilization and thereby undermine the emergences of a social contract or the creation of political communities. This conception made that many parts of the world such as in Latin America ‘there is evidence of declining support for democracy due to the perception that democracy has failed to improve people’s lives (Somolakae, 2007).

(Bardhan, 2002), in similar view opined that there is no significance relationship between democracy and development when he reported that even in some of the richest democracies of the world where the enforcement of laws may be better and subject to less corruption and arbitrariness than in developing countries, the process of enactment of those laws is subject to an enormous amount of influence peddling for contribution to campaign

finance and other prerequisites for legislatures. Over time this problem has got worse in most democracies, as elections has become frightfully expensive. When policies to be legislated are up for sale to the highest contributor to the campaign fund, development projects may not win out (the policy decision in the budget may go in favour of buying one more military air craft rather than 100 rural clinics), and it will not be much consolation to be told that the policies thus legislated will be implemented well by the bureaucracy and the court system under a democracy (Bardhan, 2002). The above submission revealed that, there is problem of linkages between democratic regimes and provision of social welfare services to the people; in essence democracy does not always reflect the wishes of the voters, and does not always bring development.

In similar opinion, (Przeworski, 1990) study, observed that democratic government may be less capable of managing development. The reasoning here according to him is that, development involved changes and that change may affect some voters negatively, while at the same time benefiting others. To this extent, the study argued that, because of this reality, governments seeking re-election could be more inclined to avoid making tough economic choices out of fear of losing support of some groups. This would either slow down development or hinder it. This dilemma may not be faced by an authoritarian regime. From this view, (Przeworski, 1990) is of the view that, there is little evidence of correlation between democracy and development.

Consequently, (Przeworski, 2007) in another study examined his earlier findings on relationship between political regimes and economic development. His analysis of political regimes shows that while the part to democracy are varied, once established for whatever reasons, democracy survive in developed countries. Contrary to long existing arguments, political regimes do not affect the rate of investment and of the growth of total income. But

since population grow faster under dictatorships, per capital income increase more rapidly under democracies. The study discovered that there is correlation between democracy and development.

In this regard, one can convincingly assert that the long existing findings that democracy is prerequisite to development no longer relevant because of the recent findings that have emerged and contradicted the positions of this perception. For instance, examples of countries like Japan, China and other Asian countries which have recorded some levels of development, yet, they are authoritarian and less politically open states, have come to revalidate the argument that democracy is not prerequisite to development. Similarly, quantitative study by (William et al, 2009), proved that correlation exists between levels of income and aspect of good governance such as market capitalism and liberal democracy. The study though significant but did not prove the direct relationship between democracy and economic development vice versa.

Meanwhile, the above theoretical and empirical exploitations have not resolved our problem of whether there is positive and significant correlation between democracy and development, because both the two opposing sides have used both cases studies and empirical studies to support their arguments. The above theoretical findings made their analysis on cross countries. However, we shall examine the infrastructure development in Enugu State since the fourth republic.

Democratic Governance and Infrastructural development in Enugu State

The return to democratic rule in Enugu State on May 29, 1999 was welcomed by the over three million citizens of the state as a great relief from decades of maladministration and underdevelopment brought about by successive military administrations. Enugu, the capital of

Enugu State which was the headquarter of the former Eastern Region, where the foremost nationalists like Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, Dr. Akanu Ibiam, Professor Eyo-Ita, among others once resided and conducted their political activities, witnessed serious decay in terms of infrastructure just as its economy dropped abysmally due to lack of focus by the military juntas that administered its affairs.

Dr. Chimaroke Nnamani's Administration

The return to full-fledged democratic governance in 1999 with the emergence of Dr. Chimaroke Nnamani as the executive governor, Enugu State began to experience good governance with the provision of several infrastructures and amenities that lifted the state to the rank of developed state in Nigeria. Nnamani was mindful of the fact that Enugu occupied a prime position as the political capital of the Eastern region and made giant strides to development infrastructures in the areas of roads, housing, educational sector among others. The negative impact and scope of the ravaging decay in social infrastructure, public utilities, human and social services, experienced under the military was gradually erased by the democratic regime of Dr. Nnamani.

Highlights of his Governance

Education

As Governor, Dr. Chimaroke Nnamani established District Education Centers in the state, conceived and built the permanent campus of the Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), constructed and handed over to the Federal Government, the Enugu Campus of the Nigerian Law School, and also constructed and handed over to the Nigerian Air Force, the Airforce Comprehensive High School at Agbani. His administration also established new Special Science Schools in different parts of the state, carried out the renovation of public primary and secondary schools and provided them with school desks and teachers' tables and chairs as well.

Health

Being a medical doctor, it was no surprise that health was a top priority to Governor Nnamani. His administration established four district hospitals and 19 cottage hospitals in the state. A partnership with the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) saw to the rehabilitation and upgrade of many healthcare facilities under the Partnership for Transforming Health Systems (PATHS I & II). The flagship project of the administration in the health sector, however, was apparently the transformation of the former General Hospital at Parklane, GRA, Enugu, into the present ESUT Teaching Hospital and ESUT College of Medicine. The massive project involved the construction of new buildings, refurbishing of existing ones and the provision of modern equipment that enabled the facility to pass the accreditation of the relevant authorities in the health cum education sectors.

Infrastructure

Road construction and rehabilitation were areas that won the Nnamani administration's early popular claim. Among the rural road networks undertaken by the administration were the Awgu-Ndeabor Road, Ozalla-Agbani Road, Agbani-Akpugo-Amagunze Road, Amechi-Obeagu-Amodu-Umueze Road, Oghe-Aguobu-Umumba Road, Aguobu-Ugwuoba Road, Oji-Awgu Road, Nsukka urban roads, University of Nigeria roads, Nsukka-Ibagwa Road, OboloAfor-Ogrute Road, etc. There were also new road infrastructures like the Nyaba Bridge, and the Ebeano bypass linking NBL Ama Brewery at 9th Mile Corner with the Enugu-Onitsha expressway. In the Enugu metropolis, the Nnamani era witnessed the dualization of Chime Avenue as well as Rangers Avenue, Ebeano Tunnel connecting the busy Ogui Road and Garden Avenue, a new route linking Nza Street in Independence Layout with the Upper Chime Avenue in New Haven, amongst the streets rehabilitated in Abakpa Nike, Trans Ekulu, Achara Lawyout I and II Uwani, Coal Camp and so on.

Electricity

The administration pursued a policy of lighting up the rural communities with the provision of electricity. Over 130 rural communities benefitted from this intervention.

Water Supply

The administration improved public water supply in the state. Some of the interventions in the sector included the OzallaEzimo Water Scheme in Udenu LGA, expansion of Enugu Urban water supply, expansion of the Ajali River water works, reactivation of the Ede-Obala booster station for water supply to Nsukka town, Agbani/Amodu water reservoir, revival of Awhum water scheme, and the construction of hundreds of motorized boreholes in the rural communities across the state.

Governor Sullivan Chime's Administration

In April 2007, Sullivan Chime successfully vied for the post of governor of Enugu State on the platform of Peoples Democratic Party(PDP).He was sworn into office on 29 May 2007, succeeding Dr. Chimaroke Nnamani. He was re-elected on 26 April 2011. Chime mapped a 4-point agenda for development of Enugu State such as: Physical Infrastructure, Economic Expansion and Employment, Rural Development and Service Delivery. In spite of his achievements, Chime was known to shun public functions, rather preferring to send delegates than appear in person. His political reticence earned him the title "Silent Achiever".

Highlights of Sullivan's Administration

- **Physical Infrastructure:** Chime started very well as governor, reconstructing roads in Enugu urban areas, and key roads in the rural areas. The roads were of good quality and durable, complete with street lights, drainage and pedestrian sidewalks. Chime also advocated compliance with traffic laws, introduced traffic lights, solved traffic issues by dualizing roads, or creating new routes altogether. Under his administration, pipe-

borne water supply as well as electricity improved. But a few of Chime's actions have not been without controversy such as the recent demolition of the State Secretariat built during the colonial era. Some believe the demolition was needless, and more so the funds required to build the new Secretariat could have been invested in other key areas. Others point out that a new State Secretariat is appropriate given the State's growing workforce.

His administration also embarked on so many road constructions such as:

Ugwogo Nike-OpiNsukka Road; Ninth Mile-Nsude-Obioma – Abia –Udi –Oji River; Eke- Ebe- Egede- Affa- Akpakume-Aku Road; Iwollo- Oghe- Olo- Umolokpa Road and Zikavenue/bridge and Abakpa bridge etc.

- **Security:** Chime also invested in statewide security. In the second quarter of 2013, he donated 100 units each of Kia Rio and Hilux vans equipped with communication gadgets to the Enugu State Police Command for urban and rural policing respectively (despite this being a Federal Government concern). Enugu State was under his administration, declared to have the least crime rate, and one of the safest places in Nigeria.
- **Health:** Chime introduced free maternal and child healthcare in State-owned hospitals in response to the high maternal mortality ratio of 286 per 100,000 women and the Under-5 mortality of 103 per 1000 children in the South East. It was the fervent hope of the natives of Enugu State that Chime would undertake massive reforms in the health sector such as building world-class medical facilities so as to make foreign medical trips unnecessary.
- **Education:** Education has yet to get due attention under Chime, despite Chime crusading for a return of schools to the missions. Meanwhile, some schools have

recorded successes in this regard such as College of the Immaculate Conception, Chime's own Alma Mater and several other schools in Enugu Urban. But in several other communities, pupils still lack basic infrastructure and teachers. Even the State-owned Institute of Management and Technology plays host to dingy buildings, aging due to bad maintenance. City busses, multiple estates and layouts, uniform taxis, traffic lights, shopping malls, good roads, lesser crimes, and a city of lights at night; the cliché quote “growth is a slow process” has been successfully defied unarguably in Enugu State, since 29th May 2007 and the swearing in of Barr. Sullivan Iheanacho Chime the visionary Governor who changed the looks of Enugu and the minds of her citizens. Development in Enugu have since then been growing rapidly and Sullivan Chime’s government has been identified to have a strong concern on human development citing the achievements in his first term. Barrister Sullivan Chime regularized the state’s salary payment within the 25th of every month after he increase the minimum wage, clearing the arrears accumulated by past administrations, paying up gratuity and pensions, and also initiating a comprehensive healthcare plan for workers. Sullivan Chime also deemed it necessary to enhance the Education system in the state by approving 195 million naira for the rehabilitation of some public primary school and also donated 300 busses to secondary schools in the state.

- **Electricity:** He equally provided stable electricity even in rural areas and electricity connections to rural areas where there was no initial power connection and as well improved water scheme. It really doesn’t need a rocket science brain to figure that all these developments create enabling environment for a more stable economy and human development.

Governor Ifeanyi Ugwuanyi's Administration

Major Highlights of Governor Ugwuanyi's Administration include:

(a) Payment of workers' Salaries

Ugwuanyi has sustained in the past one year, the payment of workers' salaries on the 25th of every month. The N4.207b Federal Government bail-out funds received by the state meant for the payment of arrears salaries and pensions of some public servants owed by the previous administration is currently being disbursed and supervised by a joint committee comprising of representatives of organized labour, government and pensioners.

Also, the welfare of workers has received the Governor's attention as work has reached advanced stages at the Workers' Estate at Ogbeke. The government has paid 30 percent equity contribution to enable interested Enugu State civil servants from Grade Level 01 to Grade Level 10, to acquire 100 units of one-bedroom flats at Elim Estate, Ibagwa, Nike, Enugu. The beneficiaries of this scheme have since been selected through an open lottery system held recently at the Michael Okpara Square, Enugu.

(b) Security

The state government donated 17 Hilux trucks to the police and other security agencies in the past year to support their efforts apart from other logistics provided by the Governor. The Governor has doled out N100 million to the Neighborhood Watch Groups in the 472 communities in the state to serve as vigilante and complement the efforts of security agencies.

(c) Urban Rural Development

In fulfillment of the promise to catalyze urban and rural development and develop new cities in the state to boost economic activities, the government embarked on the massive development of roads across the state. The government flagged off the construction of major roads across the state. These were the AmekeNgwo-Nsude Junction Bypass, Ninth Mile Corner Bypass,

Dualisation of Opi-Nsukka Road, Abakpa Nike Road, Nike Lake Road, Ohom Orba Junction, ImilikeAni-Ezimo, Uno-Ezimo, Agu-Imilike-Ogbudu, Ada-Obollo-Etiti, Amalla-ObolloAfor, Udeno Ring Road, Enugu Road Junction, Umuezebi-Nru Junction, University Gate, Nsukka; Post Office Roundabout, Odenigbo Roundabout, Ogurugu Road, Ikenga Hotel Junction, Obechara Road Junction, Umuakashi Mechanic Village, Ikenga Hotel Junction.

Some of the roads like the Abakpa Nike Road, Nike Lake Road have been completed while others have gone beyond 70% completion. Ugwuanyi's government, in this one year, has also completed the hitherto intractable Ogbete Market and gone far with the rehabilitation of the Airport Roundabout-OrieEmene-St. Patrick's College-Eke Obinagu Road Project, Mbanefo II, New Haven. It also directed the continuous maintenance of the roads in Enugu.

(d) Agriculture

As part of rural and agricultural development initiatives, the government of Ugwuanyi initiated the construction of a 15-kilometre Inter-Town Connection, ITC, 2.5MVA Injection Sub-Station at Ezi-Nze, Udi LGA just a few days after assumption of office. This initiative will supply electricity to communities in Udi, Igbo-Etiti, and Uzo-Uwani LGAs. It will also activate businesses in these rural communities and power the Adada Dam Project as well as the Greater Nsukka Water Scheme.

(e) Education

Governor Ifeanyi Ugwuanyi of Enugu State on Thursday unveiled the ultra modern permanent site of the Post Primary School Management Board (PPSMB), saying the new edifice was another demonstration of his administration's resolve to provide quality education for the people of the state. The governor also commissioned some equipment recently procured by the

state government for technical and vocational schools in the state, during which he inspected exhibitions of craft and equipment built by talented students of technical schools.

Unveiling the PPSMB permanent site, the governor said the project will provide a conducive operational environment for workers in the state as part of the government's efforts to promote job satisfaction, efficiency and productivity among the workers.

He said his administration had also declared its unequivocal commitment to raise the standard and quality of education in the state, especially through the revitalization of regulatory bodies in the education sector in addition to the upgrading of facilities and infrastructure.

In addition to this and despite the prevailing economic climate, we approved the release of outstanding 2013, 2014 and 2015 arrears of promotion for the staff of the Board and also approved 27.5% of Teachers' enhancement allowance. Government also procured over 600 desktop computers and accessories for distribution to secondary schools in the state to enhance the ICT knowledge and skills among the students and their teachers.

(f) Health

The health sector is already receiving a breath of fresh air as the state government has, among other things, continued to sustain the well acclaimed Free Maternal Health and Child Care Programme, while ensuring the proper equipment and staffing of existing health institutions in the state. The government also is on the verge of completing the ultra-modern medical diagnostic centre in Enugu and has initiated the construction of three new Specialist Hospitals in the three Senatorial Zones of the state with the flag off of the scheme at Orba, Udenu LGA.

(g) Employment

In line with the polices on human development, youth empowerment and poverty alleviation, the state government recently appointed 600 Executive Assistants and is on the verge of making

other major appointments and reconstituting boards for parastatals in the state. Governor Ugwuanyi, equally approved the recruitment of primary teachers in the last quarter of 2016 to boost teaching-learning in the state public schools.

Conclusion

The challenges of infrastructure development in Enugu State in particular and Nigeria in general are many. This is for fact that the demand for the infrastructure surpasses the supply, and finance that will stimulate rapid provision is not there. Due to the wide gap between provision and needs, the leadership classes are in arrears in all sectors. The political situation is not encouraging to foreign investors. Again, governments do not set the priority right in infrastructure development. Projects are supposed to meet objectives, but in most cases, projects embarked upon are white elephant projects.

It is necessary to note that the democratic process should be universal and the characteristics should be the same all over the world. As such, it will be inelegant for Nigeria to have its own brand of democracy. In other words, Nigeria should key in or imbibe universal democratic norms and inculcate its ethos and tenets in the minds of its citizens. Both the leaders and the led should allow democracy to be operated in the country just as inn other civilized nations in order to enthrone good governance, accountability and transparency at all levels and in all sectors of the national life.

Furthermore, good governance will be the only antidote that can bridge the wide gap because good governance promotes accountability, reduce corruption, increase employment opportunities and therefore, minimize resource wastage through inefficiency. Good governance ensures stability (economic and political) as well as reduces the level risk associated with large and lumpy infrastructure investments. This in turn facilitates the mobilization of both public and private sectors financing resources that are critical for infrastructure development.

Consequently, Enugu State in particular and Nigeria in general have big land masses that make it impossible to connect the people with roads, national grid and potable water because of high cost of materials for infrastructure development and other challenges. Again, the corruption level in Nigeria and Enugu in particular is too high and allows incompetent hands to handle contracts. Professionals are not allowed to handle projects due to corruption. The cost of governance and recurrent expenditure are so high leaving little for capital expenditure. Also, the high level of unemployment is a disincentive to market and capital development.

Lastly, it is apparent from the assessment of democratic development and its attendant challenges that the country had wobbled democratically since it had remained a mere civilian government and not a true democratic government. The political leaders are not altruistic and have a vision of self-aggrandizement that run counter to the aspirations of the people. This is for the fact that while Nigerians are languishing in poverty, their rulers are reveling in obscene affluence.

Recommendations

It must be emphasized that in Enugu State in particular and Nigeria in general, for democracy to engender good governance there is the need for massive infrastructural development, especially in the areas of road, electricity, pipe borne water, and so forth. In addition, the issue of poverty eradication must be addressed. Governments at all levels must also exhibit budgetary discipline. Budget in our state is gradually becoming an annual ritual without any effect on government's revenue and expenditure profile.

Also, there must be a need for strengthening the legislative arm of government, so as to effectively and efficiently perform its assigned responsibilities, particularly its oversight functions, to put the executive on its toes in its service delivery function. Furthermore, legal

and electoral reforms should be carried out to do away with defective aspects as well as promote good governance. Sectoral service delivery and capacity building are equally essential to empower and strengthen sectors such as health, agriculture service, education, trade and industry, and so forth. Without these sectors optimally performing their roles, good governance may be difficult to achieve. The officials in charge of these sectors must be mobilized, motivated and trained to enable them rededicate themselves to the service of the state.

Civil Society actors also must be alive to their responsibilities, particularly as against corruption, inefficiency, ineffectiveness and general mal-administration. Citizens as well must be mobilized to always demand accountability and transparency from their leaders. Again, the anti-corruption agencies should intensify efforts in tackling pervasive corruption in the local government systems of the state in particular and country at large. For instance, local governments in Enugu State have not really facilitated rapid development at the grassroots, which is the essence of their creation.

However, it was discovered that several members of the national electoral body were card carrying members of some political parties, this shows outright partisanship, and as such adequate arrangement should be made to prevent this. In the same vein, the limit placed on the number of political associations to be registered greatly restricts the ability of the people to freely express themselves through party formation. Therefore, the role the electoral body should be restricted to party identification rather than registration.

Finally, the leadership of any state or organization must involve the peoples' participations in the administration of the state affairs for adequate planning, accountability, transparency and good governance. Equally, state governors should also allow the council heads to manage their resources, design appropriate policies and projects that suit peculiar areas for effective realization of democratic dividends.

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